

BEHAVIORAL ASPECTS OF LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *The article discusses the theories, approaches of communicative language learning. Learning presentations of grammatical knowledge that has resulted from instruction, and acquisition. Teacher roles in the terms in the learning process. Method represents the imitation, repetition, memorization and reinforcement were impressed within speaking practice with variety of drills.*

Keywords: *communication, CLT, Community Language Learning, Classroom procedures, Curriculum, Learning theories, Direct method, Imperfect modeling, Method, Negotiations.*

INTRODUCTION.

The language consists of various elements. When these are sorted from small to large, the smallest elements that make up the language are sounds. Sounds gain meaning not alone, but when combined with other elements. This merger takes place depending on some rules. The equivalents of sounds in written language are letters. Sounds and letters combine to form syllables, words and sentences. Situations such as the sequence of words in a sentence, function, meaning, creating text from words and sentences are included in the field of grammar knowledge. In the field of linguistics, the elements such as sounds, words, sentences and text that make up a language are examined in terms of structure, type, task, functioning and meaning, and various rules are laid down. In this process, the study of language knowledge, research and teaching approaches and methods are also important.

In the past, when it was called grammar, the rules about language came to mind and students were taught a set of rules. Over time, this limited understanding and practice has changed. Nowadays, language knowledge is taught in order for an individual to understand the language well, communicate, and improve their mental skills. Language knowledge is not only a means of communication, but also the subject of language recognition and learning. Because language knowledge is necessary to use and develop a language correctly. Today, grammar teaching has been discussed in detail with the constructivist approach, and the goals, approaches, methods and processes of grammar teaching have been redefined. This together with the approach, the purpose of grammar teaching has been determined as teaching the language itself, not the rules.

Literature review. In the last three decades, seeing the importance and benefits of researching teacher effectiveness in foreign language teaching to the teaching process and the parties affected by this process, several researchers have attempted to shed light on this construct. Studies investigating the effectiveness of foreign language teachers revealed results about the personality traits of the teacher, her/his methods of delivering the lesson and his level of information about the foreign language. Brosh [1] investigated the characteristics of effective language teachers as perceived by foreign language teachers and students in Israel with a questionnaire and interviews. The following characteristics emerged from this study:

Knowledge and command of the target language, Ability to organize, explain, and clarify, as well as to arouse and sustain interest and motivation among students, Fairness to students by showing neither favoritism nor prejudice, Availability to students [2].

Barnes and Lock [3] investigated attributes of effective lecturers of English as a foreign language as perceived by students in a Korean university through a free writing instrument which asked 105 students to write about the attributes of effective English as a foreign language (EFL) lecturers. The results of the study indicated that students feel that lecturer to student rapport is essential to build atmospheres of respect and understanding in EFL classes; 2) existing and prospective lecturers should know that the degree of lecturer enthusiasm and preparation are very obvious to students and major factors influencing classroom atmosphere and motivation; 3) diverse views about the type and level of error correction will be a source of conflict unless lecturers make the effort to align student expectations with their own, and be sensitive to student self-esteem; 4) existing and prospective EFL practitioners should be aware that students appreciate their efforts to employ a participatory approach” (pp. 148-9).

Wichadee and Orawiwatnakul [4] collected data with a questionnaire from 192 students at Bangkok University. The results of their study indicated that both low and high proficiency students rated “effective language teacher skills” in order of importance as follows: organization and communication skills, socio-affective skills, and organization and communication skills. In a recent paper, Salahshour and Hajizadeh [5] attempted to shed light on characteristics of effective EFL instructors through a 58-item questionnaire in Iran. They listed some of the most important features of an effective and successful EFL teacher as follows:

- Having interest in his/her job
- Having a sense of responsibility towards his/her job
- Being enthusiastic and lively
- Being self-confident
- Being punctual
- Encouraging students to use the target language at all times
- Providing explicit grammar correction
- Providing detailed explanation during reading and listening tasks
- Emphasizing frequent oral quizzes
- Emphasizing all skills, especially speaking
- Having knowledge of subject matter
- Having the ability to communicate ideas effectively
- Having the ability to answer the students’ questions
- Having respect for students
- Being kind and friendly
- Encouraging participation
- Creating motivation in students
- Helping to increase the students’ self-confidence during learning
- Taking students’ feedback about the class into consideration
- Using the class time wisely
- Maintaining class order.

In another study, Brown [6], investigated approximately 1600 students’ and 49 teachers’ perceptions of effective foreign language teaching through a 24-item questionnaire at the University of Arizona. The results of the study indicated that the students are in favor of a grammar-based approach whereas their teachers preferred a more communicative classroom. The results of the study also pointed to the need for foreign language teachers to seek out their students’

perspectives actively and to engage them in brief classroom discussions about the rationale behind certain instructional strategies.

Research Methodology. This study is a quantitative survey since it comprises of data collection through a questionnaire aiming to describe the perceptions of pre-service EFL teachers regarding the characteristics of effective English language teachers. As Gay, Mills and Airasian state “survey research can be used to gather information about a group’s beliefs, attitudes, behaviors, and demographic composition”.

Analysis and results. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Methods of Teaching Grammar when the methods of teaching grammar applied in our world from the past to the present are examined, we come across a long list. It is seen that different methods are applied according to each period, language and approach. These can be listed as 'Grammar-Translation Method, Natural Method, Direct Teaching Method, Active Method, Auditory-Verbal (Listen-Speak) Method, Audiovisual Method, Traditional Method, Intuition Method'. Some methods that are considered important are described below.

Grammar-Translation Method: The purpose of this method is to teach students to read, translate texts in a foreign language, then listen and speak through grammar rules and translation. In grammar teaching, the rule was presented first, explained and then shown in a sentence. The sentences given to the students were usually formed sentences established to teach the rules of grammar. These were given separately from the text. Since the language teaching studies were carried out by memorization, imitation and repetition, the students were bored and the lessons were conducted in a single order (Puren, 2004, Rodríguez Seara, 2004).

Direct Teaching Method: This method is a combined and slightly improved version of the natural method with the grammar-translation method. Knowledge of language is treated as a complementary element to speaking and reading and is taught indirectly. In grammar teaching, the rules are taught indirectly by acting from examples, without being explained in detail. Knowledge of language is not a goal but a means (Puren, 2004, Rodríguez Seara,2004). This method, which has been applied in the field of language teaching for many years, has been replaced by the active method in later years.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK	
<p style="text-align: center;">Knowledge of traditional languages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Language knowledge issues are determined and explained by language science experts. • Every subject suitable for language science is taken, examined in depth and entered into the finest details. • Most of the rules taught are not used in everyday language. Used for samples the texts are taken from great literary authors. * The rules of the language are usually memorized. 	<p style="text-align: center;">New language knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Language knowledge issues language education specialists and it is determined and explained by educators. * Definitions and rules that improve language skills appropriate to the student's needs are discussed. * Emphasis is placed on the use of language. Texts in everyday language are also included. * Scientific approach, methods and rules in the field of education are used. * Priority is given to discovering the logic of language.

OBJECTIVES	
<p>Knowledge of traditional languages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Language knowledge is taken as a mandatory and basic purpose. • Students are taught the entire content of language knowledge. * Grammar education is necessary to prepare students for a higher school. 	<p>New language knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Language knowledge is a tool for language education. • It is taught in order to improve students' language and mental skills. * Language knowledge teaching is carried out, which is necessary in the new educational understanding.
content	
<p>Knowledge of traditional languages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The whole content of language knowledge is focused on. • All subjects are taught intensively from primary school onwards. • The topics of the previous year are reviewed every year. * The grammar program repeats in most classes and is similar to each other. * Language events are taught by explaining them. • The main content is grammar rules and vocabulary. 	<p>New language knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Focuses on grammar knowledge events in everyday language. • Those necessary for language and mental skills are taught. * Intensive and useful language knowledge is taught by giving little-used language events at a simple level. * Language knowledge content is given gradually and evenly from the first school. * Language events are taught together with explanation, process and condition information. • The main content is sentences and text.

In the table above, basic information about two types of language knowledge is given. This table can be prepared in even more detail. As it can be seen, the new grammar aims to teach logic rather than form, the language itself rather than the rules of the language. It places the student, not the grammar rules, at the center of the teaching process, and adopts a grammar understanding appropriate for the student. The dissemination of this understanding depends on the fact that teachers are aware of the new language knowledge and teach it well.

Conclusion/Recommendations.

In this study, we aim to gather information on how promising Turkish elt teachers perceive the characteristics of an effective foreign language teacher. The results of the study, in accordance with previous studies, show that the ELT Department, female and full-time students have an idea that an effective foreign language teacher should teach communicatively. Foreign Language teachers believe that students should be indirectly corrected when they produce verbal errors instead of resorting to direct correction (e.g., repeating them correctly instead of directly saying that they are wrong). They also believe that an effective foreign language teacher should be well versed in target culture.

The participants from the ELT department evaluate the foreign language teachers who allow the use of mother tongue in responding to test questions, give priority to indirect correction, teach the language by having students complete specific tasks rather than grammar-focused

exercises, have students respond to commands physically in the foreign language, speak the foreign language with native-like control of both grammar and accent significantly, and who are knowledgeable about the culture of the target language more effective than those from the EL&L department do. This study is limited to 404 participants from only two state universities in Uzbekistan where English is taught as a foreign language and the data of the study is collected by a questionnaire and analyzed quantitatively. Since there is no empirical evidence for the correlation between the prospective teachers' perceptions of the effective foreign language teachers and their GPAs, further studies may focus on investigating the university entrance exam scores of the students, especially their scores of English test (LYS-5), with regard to their GPAs, time of the classes, and other variables. Another limitation of this study is that it has collected data at one time.

Further studies can be designed with a longitudinal approach; that is to say, data can be collected from the prospective teachers and they may be compared to the data collected after they become in-service teachers, so as to analyze whether there is a perceptual change. To further our understanding of perceptions of the prospective teachers of English from different majors, characteristics of effective foreign language teachers can be investigated through designing qualitative and mixed method studies which can provide in-depth analysis of the participants' experiences.

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